

The AQUASERV Data Landscaping Survey of current data management practice - instruments

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This survey is being conducted by WP3 as part of deliverable D3.2: Data Landscaping. For this deliverable we need to collect information about the data produced by AQUASERV TA services. This will allow us to recommend how to optimise the findability and reusability of data that is produced by AQUASERV TA projects, and to increase the interoperability and utility of those data. D3.2 will also be the basis on which all beneficiaries in AQUASERV can apply for internal funding to improve their data management and enhance their data interoperability. Therefore, the more information we have about the AQUASERV services, the better our recommendations can be and the more likely it is that applications to the internal funding (T3.3) will be successful.

Our focus is on the TA services that produce data: either data coming directly from instruments, or data that will be gathered by the TA scientists using lab/station facilities. It is likely that the most complete answers will come from the actual labs/stations that host those services; as this survey is being sent to the access/liaison officers of the AQUASERV beneficiaries, they will be responsible for gathering the necessary responses from the partners in their network. Whether the access officer fills in this survey for each of their partners or instead asks the actual service providers to do that, is a decision that the access officers themselves can make.

There is a wide range of the platforms and services offered by the partners in AQUASERV. For our purposes, we divide these into two groups: Instruments (being any instrument that produces digital data in the form of files or as a readout); and Activities (being all other platforms/services, where the scientist performs some set of actions and records the data themselves). We have created separate surveys for these two categories as there are slightly different questions; therefore, each access officer will therefore need to work on both.

In this Instruments survey, we are interested in the data of those instruments *and* in the data management practises of the service provider for those instruments.

Please complete this survey separately for each instrument type that the AQUASERV station/lab/partners individually offer.

There could be a wide range of actual instruments that are offered for the different platform categories of AQUASERV, and we need to have information for *each* type of instrument. The questions asked in this survey concern: the types of data from the instruments, the protocols that are provided, the standards that are used, and how those data are managed. **If the separate instruments for a category are very similar, it is possible to answer for all instruments in one survey as long as it is clear in your**

answers which aspects of each reply belong to which particular instrument (e.g. "instrument X operating procedures can be found on <https://xxx>, instrument Y operating procedures can be found on <https://yyy>"). **Otherwise, please fill in one survey for each instrument in each relevant category.**

Given the breadth of different services offered, it is difficult to generalise but we hope it is clear what we are asking. If you need further clarification on the questions asked in this survey, please contact aquaserv-wp3@groups.emdesk.com AND atkacz@ualg.pt

Definitions

- **beneficiary**: the organisation in AQUASERV that are receiving the direct funding for TA
- **service provider**: the bodies (persons/stations/institutes) that offer the access services for the TA programme of AQUASERV
- **service** (a.k.a. *facilities/platforms/equipment*): the individual services offered by the service providers. For our purposes we further break this down to the level of individual **instruments** (e.g. a plankton scanner, microscopes) or individual **activities** (e.g. the act of collecting samples)
- **station**: the place where the services are offered (e.g. a marine station, a laboratory facility)
- **digital object**: any digital file (e.g. a spreadsheet, an image, a software file) or set of files (e.g. a set of images produced by one run of an instrument)
- **raw data** is a digital file or files containing data coming directly from an instrument or an observational study
- **intermediate data** is a digital file(s) that are derived from (raw) data through a subsequent analyses after collection
- **metadata** are data digital that *describes* raw or intermediate data (i.e. the who, what, where, when, why and how of the data). Normally provided in some type of text file.
- **FAIR** digital objects that are Findable (online), Accessible (once found), Interoperable (standardised and using controlled vocabularies), Reusable (provided with a provenance description of how they were created)

Privacy statement

The information collected here are to be used for D3.2. When published, none of person information collected here will be included. The names we collected are purely for AQUASERV purposes and we will only contact those people for questions regarding AQUASERV. At the end of the project, these names will be deleted. You can contact us on aquaserv-wp3@groups.emdesk.com if you wish to have your name removed before then.

* Indicates required question

How to deliver this survey(s)

Administrative questions

For repeated surveys, only the first two questions need to be filled in

1. 1. Which station are you, and which service are you describing here? Example *
 answer: "CCMAR-Faro, Sequencing platform: Oxford Nanopore Minion"

2. 2. Who is compiling this information? (position, name and email address) *

3. 3. Person who will be responsible for data management at the service provider *
 (name and email address, ORCID if available)

- 4. 4. Is there someone at the service provider who understands FAIR data, Open data, and data management and could help TA users with this? If yes, give their contact details (name, email, ORCID). *

Technical questions

Fill in for each instance of this survey. If answering for multiple instruments please make it clear which part of the answer is for which particular instrument

- 5. 5. What is the type of type of digital object(s) (e.g spreadsheet, digital images) and what type of file(s) (e.g xlsx, jpg, csv, fastq) is/are produced by this service? *

Please provide information about that format (e.g. as provided by the instrument company or the URL to the instrument's webpage) or at least its full format name.

- 6. 6a. Are there (Standard) Operating Procedures (i.e. protocols or SOPs) that are followed for this instrument/service/device? *

SOPs are agreed protocols (i.e., not protocols used by someone and modified at will by others) that allow for repeatable measurements. They can be as simple as a small note next to a machine (e.g., switch on, place the sample in a holder, click on the green button, wait, write down the value, remove the sample, switch off) or as detailed as a multi-page explanation, such as this example of nitrogen concentration measurement: [Nitrogen Concentration Measurement SOP](#). You may store your SOPs on a piece of paper, in an internal database, or online

- 7. 6. If yes to question 6a: please give the URLs (links) to those. If they are not available online, give the contact details of the person who can provide these to us. *

- 8. 7. Can anyone at the station assist/train/advice the AQUASERV TA users in publishing their data from the service? *

Tick all that apply.

- yes, we can assist
- yes, but only with general advice
- no, we do not have that expertise

- 9. 8. Does your station have a/any data management plan(s) that you follow for particular services or activities? *
- If yes, provide the link to that DMP or indicate how we can see a copy of it/them.

- 10. 9. Does your station have organised data management workflows, to turn collected/raw data into FAIR data? *

Tick all that apply.

- Yes
- No
- Partially
- We are working on it

11. 10. Does the naming of the data files follow a standard format -- either created by the instrument or created by your organisation -- or is the user of the service free to create their own filenames?

If there is a standard, please give examples (for example Nanopore_JohnSmith_26062024.fastq) and a short description, i.e. equipment_username_data.extension)

12. 11a. Do the digital objects produced by the instrument have associated metadata. Metadata may be placed in an independent file, separate spreadsheet or may even be a part of the data.

By metadata we understand any type of data describing the main (raw) data. For example instrument settings, experiment time and duration, etc.

13. 11b. If yes to the question above: is that metadata also made available for the TA user to access/copy/take home?
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14. 12a. Do the digital objects produced by the instrument have associated intermediate files (e.g. raw as well as processed images, analysed or semi-analysed data) that are produced separately.
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15. 12b. If yes to the question above: are those additional data also made available for the TA user to access/copy/take home?
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16. 13a. In the **data** produced by the instrument, are standard vocabularies used ?
These vocabularies are sets of standardised terms with persistent and unique identifiers (called PIDs, normally a link to a website with a description of such a term, a list of related terms, etc.). Using standard vocabularies greatly improves interoperability of data (i.e. researchers from other places/institutes are able to quickly understand what has been measured/sampled in your lab)

Examples of vocabularies:

[ISO standards](#) - e.g. SI units as length in meters (m) rather than inches (in)

[WoRMS](#) - e.g. Oomycota rather than Oomycetes

(<https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=172230>)

[MarineRegions](#) - e.g. Latvian part of the Baltic Sea rather than "Baltic" or "Latvian Baltic" or "20 km NE from a city of X". Such a region comes with a unique identification number (here 25669) and a dedicated website link - i.e. PID (<http://marineregions.org/mrgid/25669>)

ENVO - e.g. concentration of organic nitrogen anion in soil rather than "soil N" or "N conc". Such term has its own PID (website link) of

https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/envo/classes/http%253A%252F%252Furl.obolibrary.org%252Fobo%252FENVO_3200066

There are other vocabularies lists that may be more relevant to your research field.

Also, to check whether your terms/description can be considered as standard vocabulary you can either use automated tools and libraries like:

OpenRefine: *A tool for working with messy data, it supports reconciliation against various vocabularies.*

SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language): *Used for validating RDF data against vocabularies.*

PySHACL: *A Python library for SHACL validation.*

RDFLib: *A Python library to work with RDF, useful for parsing and validating against vocabularies.*

or manually inspect a sample of your data and metadata:

Extract Terms: *Identify the terms used in your metadata fields.*

Compare Terms: *Compare these terms with the terms in the known vocabularies (e.g. WoRMS, MarineRegions)*

Consistency Check: *Ensure that the terms are used consistently according to the definitions in the vocabulary.*

17. 13b. If yes to question 13a: please provide the names and home page (web address) of those vocabularies.

18. 13c. If no to question 13a, how are the data described/labelled so that they can be understood by the data user?

19. 13d. Can you provide us with some example data files for this instrument upon request?

20. 14a. In the **metadata** produced by the instrument, are standard vocabularies (e.g. [ISO standards](#), [WoRMS](#), [MarineRegions](#), ENVO...) used?

21. 14b. If yes to question 14A: please provide the names and home page (web address) of those vocabularies.

22. 14c. If no to question 14a: how are metadata described/labelled so that they can be understood?

23. 14d. Can you provide us with some example metadata files for this instrument upon request?

Additional questions

Fill in for each instance of this survey. If answering for multiple instruments/activities please make it clear which part of the answer is for which particular instrument/activity

24. 15. Are the instruments in your station given **unique** IDs or names (to which they can be referred to for re-usability purposes in data)? *

For example, a code or name that only that instrument has and is recorded somewhere—e.g., you may call the microplate reader "blue" or "red" or "Thermo," "the one with luminescence," but such terms would mean little to others. We are looking for IDs such as (e.g.) BMG Labtech SPECTROstar Nano 601-101-12 (catalog name). Your instrument may also have a unique ID given by the manufacturer, which will allow you to know which machine produced the data in case you have multiple copies of the same model.

Tick all that apply.

- yes
- no
- some
- not unique ones

25. 16. If yes to the question above: how are these IDs/names constructed (it is easier to just give some examples)

26. 17. Is there an internal database where the data produced by the service is archived? *

Tick all that apply.

- yes
- no
- no, but we are building one

27. 18. If no to the question above: if AQUASERV could offer advice and training, would the station like to set up/use a database for this service?

Tick all that apply.

- yes
 no
 will need to consult with higher-ups

28. 19. If yes to the question on " internal database": is this database accessible?

Tick all that apply.

- yes, internally and externally
 only internally, but we can make the data accessible upon request
 only internally, and these data cannot be made accessible upon request

29. 20. If yes to the question on " internal database": what type of database it is (e.g. MongoDB, MS Access files, MS Excel files, googlesheets, relational database).

Your instrument may not allow for storing any data, requiring you to export and store it in a dedicated database. However, many modern instruments can store data on the internal/connected computer or cloud. You might be using such a database directly through the instrument's software without knowing its type. To check, look for files like config.php, database.yml, or those with a .env extension. There are also many more advanced methods to identify the database type. If you struggle with this, please let us know if you would like our assistance.

30. 21. If yes to the question on "internal database": how are the data and the metadata archived?

Tick all that apply.

- metadata and data in the same database
 data in one database, metadata in another database
 only data are in the database
 only metadata are in the database

General questions

Only need to fill these in once per service provider

31. 22. If AQUASERV offered data management and FAIR data training, would anyone at your station be interested (please be honest!).

Tick all that apply.

- yes
 no
 perhaps
 probably not

32. 23. Is additional data collected/produced by your service that is typically discarded (not published) that in other contexts could be valuable? Possibly “null” data, or “noise”. If yes, why are these data typically discarded?

33. 24. Do you offer the use of electronic laboratory notebooks that TA users could use?

34. 25. Does your station commonly publish data produced by your services to community repositories? If yes, please indicate for which services and which repositories are used.

35. 26. Can you identify any areas where you believe the current procedures for the management of data could be improved in your station?

36. 27. Any other information or discussion you would like to provide...

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